

The effect of empathy with nature and humans on conservation behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Fostering positive relationships between humans and nature is critical to conservation efforts globally, yet little research has considered the effects of empathy with nature and empathy with humans on conservation behaviour. This study examined the relationships between empathy with nature and humans on conservation behaviour. In 2024, 329 residents of Turku, Finland, over the age of 15 completed a survey containing validated measures of empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy and conservation behaviour in the public and private spheres. We found that empathy with nature was consistently a strong predictor of conservation behaviour and behavioural intention in the public sphere. Cognitive empathy was a positive predictor of conservation behaviour intention in the private sphere, while affective empathy had a weak negative effect on conservation behaviour in the public sphere. These different predictive capacities highlight the importance of moving from general measures of empathy with humans to measures including cognitive and affective components in conservation behaviour research and practice.

1. Introduction

Creating a relational view of ‘all of us’ and bridging the known divide between ‘us’ humans and ‘other species’ is critical to addressing the global biodiversity crisis (EEA, 2023). The concept of ‘empathy’ can support a more respectful co-habitation of humans and other beings on the planet (Schnegg & Breyer, 2024) and is a route to sustainable interactions with the biosphere (Brown et al., 2019). In its widest sense, empathy means sharing and understanding the internal states of others (Zaki, 2020), including the recognition and/or experience of emotion (Jolliffe & Farrington, 2004).

In trait studies, scholars focus on dispositional empathy with nature (hereafter empathy with nature) - “the understanding and sharing of the emotional experience, particularly distress, of the natural world” (Tam, 2013, p. 93). Previous studies show that individuals with high empathy with nature are more concerned about how their actions harm nature (Czap et al., 2012). They also have stronger environmental attitudes (e.g., towards air pollution, water pollution and noise pollution) (Ienna

et al., 2022; Li et al., 2024; Tam, 2013), and a higher willingness to engage in environmental protection in the private sphere (Wang et al., 2023). These results confirm the empathy-altruism hypothesis which posits that individuals with a strong feeling or emotion of empathy are more likely to behave altruistically (Batson & Weeks, 1996).

While empathy with nature has long been studied in environmental research and empathy with humans in social science research, holistic consideration of both empathy with nature and empathy with humans are less frequently considered together in trait research. Key exceptions are work by Tam (2013) and Sevillano et al. (2017) who found that empathy with nature and empathy with humans were only weakly to moderately correlated. Li et al. (2024) found that empathy with nature has a stronger predictive effect on conservation behaviour than empathy with humans, even after assessing confounding effects, which supports earlier empirical work by Tam (2013).

Separate research has considered dispositional empathy with nature through the proxy of ‘inclusion of self in nature’. Schultz (2000) proposed that environmental concern is tied to a person’s sense of self and

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the degree to which they define themselves as connected with all living things (nature). People who see themselves independent from nature are egoistic in that concern for the environment will be motivated by self-interest (egoistic concerns). At the other extreme, people who see themselves fully connected or as part of nature will desire to gain rewards for all living things (biospheric concerns). People who focus on other people including the community, children, and all people have high altruistic concerns. The inclusion of nature theory (Schultz, 2002) assumes that these concerns are associated with empathy in terms of perspective taking. i.e., greater inclusion of self in nature can result from taking the perspective of animals being harmed by nature (biospheric) or people being harmed by nature (altruistic). Separately, research has assessed human- and animal-oriented empathy (Paul, 2000). Significant positive associations have been found between human compassion for animals (human-animal empathy) and for people (human-human empathy) (Cardoso et al., 2022), and between empathy levels, gender, companion animal ownership and attitudes to animals (Taylor & Signal, 2005).

Despite these works, there is not enough empirical evidence on how empathy with humans, operationalised as cognitive and affective empathy, relates to both empathy with nature and conservation behaviour. Cognitive empathy refers to the ability to infer or understand another person's perspective or emotional state (Davis, 1983). Affective empathy refers to our emotional response to a person's thoughts or feelings (Brown et al., 2019; Hatfield et al., 2009). Studying the multi-form relationships between cognitive and affective empathy and empathy with nature is important to improve the construct validity of empathy measures and its connection to behaviour (Hall & Schwartz, 2022), and also to further elaborate the empathy-altruism hypothesis.

Here we consider the effects of empathy in relation to public and private sphere conservation behaviour (Barbett et al., 2020), given that empathy and behaviour can vary depending on whether or not the conservation behaviours are publicly viewable (Powell & Roberts, 2017).

Public sphere conservation behaviours involve environmental citizenship (e.g., voting for nature conservation and attending meetings on nature conservation issues) while private sphere behaviours have direct environmental consequences and focus on activities at the personal or household level (Barbett et al., 2020; Stern, 2000) (e.g., conservation activities within one's own garden). We consider both intentions to engage in public and private conservation behaviours over the coming 12 months, and past behaviour in these areas. For simplicity, hereafter we refer to these terms as conservation behaviour intention and conservation behaviour, respectively.

In this paper, we aim to examine the relationships between empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy with humans and conservation behaviour in the private and public spheres. Using a case study from Turku, Finland, we address this aim through the following research objectives:

1. To examine the associations between empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy with humans and conservation behaviour (both past conservation behaviour and intention) in public and private spheres;
2. To explore the confounding effects of socio-demographic factors (age, gender and education) on empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy with humans and conservation behaviour in public and private spheres;
3. To develop a model showing the effects of empathy with nature, and cognitive and affective empathy with humans on conservation behaviour in public and private spheres.

2. Theoretical background and guiding hypotheses

2.1. The associations between empathy with nature and humans

Research examining general global measures of empathy with nature and empathy with humans have found that these constructs are weakly correlated (Gómez-Leal et al., 2021; Paul, 2000; Tam, 2013). Trait-based research suggests that affective empathy is conceptually and empirically distinct from cognitive empathy (Reniers et al., 2011; Shamay-Tsoory et al., 2009), but cognitive empathy can be a precursor to emotion contagion (when someone experiences the same emotion as another person through e.g., mimicking facial expressions, movements, and vocalizations of others) (Ekman, 2003).

No studies have assessed the relationships between empathy with nature and cognitive and affective empathy for humans, and therefore hypothetical associations need to be treated as exploratory. It is plausible for moderate positive associations to be found between empathy for nature and empathy for humans when people are free from contexts where they need to pit empathy for animals against empathy for humans (Cameron et al., 2019, 2022). While not tested in this study, the relationships between these empathy constructs could change if survey participants are asked to make moral trade-offs between saving human and animal lives (see Amiot & Bastian, 2015; Topolski et al., 2013 for research on such trade-offs).

2.2. The effects of empathy on behaviour

Research on inclusion of self in nature and connectedness to nature shows that individuals with stronger nature relatedness generally exhibit a deeper empathy with the natural world and a stronger willingness to engage in conservation behaviours (Brown et al., 2019; Schultz, 2000). Building on the empathy-altruism hypothesis (Batson & Weeks, 1996), Brown et al. (2019) introduced the empathy-sustainability hypothesis which posits that empathy – through processes of perspective taking and emotional connection, provides the motivational basis for conservation behaviours. This hypothesis is supported by recent works showing that empathy with nature positively predicts conservation behaviour (Jing et al., 2022; Tam, 2013), particularly in the private sphere (Wang et al., 2023). Empathy with nature has also been a positive predictor of wetland visit behaviour (Chen et al., 2023) and tourist's conservation behaviour intentions (Chen et al., 2024).

However, little is known about how empathy with humans affects conservation behaviour, and therefore it is important to explore relationships, which have a theoretical basis in research on pro-social action and empathy. Research on pro-social action has shown that it is critical to distinguish between different dimensions of empathy because they can uniquely influence behaviour (Decety & Cowell, 2014). Moderate to strong relationships have been found between cognitive empathy and pro-social behaviour such as helping behaviour (Marjanovic et al., 2012; Weng et al., 2015), injustice sensitivity (Decety & Yoder, 2016), and compassion for others (Batson et al., 1997; Kang et al., 2025).

However, weaker or no effects have been found between affective empathy and behaviour. For example, affective empathy responses can lead to personal distress and inaction in individuals who cannot clearly differentiate between their internal states and those of others (Eisenberg & Miller, 1987). For those who can clearly differentiate between their own and other's internal states, arousal can cause personal distress or pro-social action (Batson & Coke, 1981). We see this in more recent studies where negative affect including anxiety and personal stress associated with interactions with others can in some cases increase helpfulness (Ilies et al., 2013), while in other cases it can relate to helping ones' own needs or avoidance (Kang et al., 2025). Similarly, empathetic experiences and helping behaviour in friendships can be undermined by frequent sharing of negative emotions (Takamatsu et al.,

2025), or when they perceive empathetic opportunities as emotionally draining as is often seen in ‘empathy distress fatigue’ (Klimecki & Singer, 2012).

A large body of literature has also shown that empathy is prone to various biases including in-group preference and psychic and psychological numbing, which lead to reduced emotional sensitivity to overwhelming events or misfortune of large number of individuals (Cikara et al., 2011; Fetherstonhaugh et al., 1997; Slovic et al., 2011). For example, empathy favours the familiar (Cikara et al., 2011), which means that people exhibit preferential responses with close ones and avoid empathising with strangers (particular in situations without information about them) because it is seen as taxing (Cameron et al., 2019). In the context of conservation behaviour, this could mean that people may feel more empathy for familiar species and those that resemble us such as charismatic species (Griffin et al., 2020).

2.3. The associations between socio-demographic factors, empathy with nature and humans and conservation behaviour

There is overwhelming evidence to suggest that females show statistically higher levels of empathy and pro-social behaviour and intentions than males (Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004; Jolliffe & Farrington, 2004; Silke et al., 2018). Studies have reported an advantage for women in self-reports of empathy (Baez et al., 2017; Di Tella et al., 2020) and understanding of others (Fischer et al., 2017). Females also have a greater tendency than men to exhibit environmental concern and engage in conservation behaviour than men, which has been attributed to females being socialized more than males to value the needs of other beings (Zelezny et al., 2000), and the different roles of men and women established through evolution (Christov-Moore et al., 2014). However, some studies have indicated that men can show higher levels of affective empathy than females, particularly in situations involving strangers that require the helper’s initiative (Eagly & Crowley, 1986).

Empathy with humans and demographic variables such as age, sex and socioeconomic status might also confound the relationships between empathy with nature, attitudes and conservation behaviour (Li et al., 2024). Hence it is important to examine the correlations between empathy with nature and behaviour when empathy for humans and socio-demographic factors is controlled for. Also, the relationships between cognitive and affective empathy and pro-social behaviour vary depend on context. For example, in situations of conflict, cognitive empathy has enabled people to listen to other people’s points of view, while the triggering of affective empathy had no significant effect on behaviour (Van Lissa et al., 2017). To enhance the internal validity of

the study, we therefore tested the confounding effects of socio-demographics and empathy with humans on the relationships between empathy with nature and conservation behaviour intention and conservation behaviour in the public and private spheres.

In the light of these findings, we propose the following hypotheses (H):

H1. empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy with humans will be weakly to moderately correlated.

H2. Empathy with nature and cognitive empathy with humans will have moderate to strong positive effects on conservation behaviour while affective empathy with humans will have weaker effects on behaviour.

H3. Females will have higher empathy with nature, cognitive and affective empathy with humans, and will show stronger conservation behaviours.

H4. Socio-demographics and cognitive and affective empathy may confound the relationships between empathy with nature and conservation behaviour.

Fig. 1 presents an overview of the model used for testing the four hypotheses.

3. Methods

3.1. Study context

Outdoor recreation in nature has traditionally formed part of Finnish national identity (Periäinen, 2006). A public online survey of adult Finns about their understanding of human-nature relations found discourses of wellbeing, conservation, ecoanxiety, pro-environmentalism, outdoor activity and enjoying nature (Raatikainen et al., 2024). Environmental awareness among Finns is also quite high (Hyry, 2017). Finns generally understand the main causes of climate change and the roots of biodiversity loss (Ratinen & Linnanen, 2022). The study was conducted in Turku, located in the Southwest coast of Finland. Turku is one of the countries’ most populated cities (201,863 inhabitants; Statistics Finland, 2023).

3.2. Participants and sampling procedure

The study received Human Research Ethics Approval at the University of Helsinki (decision number: 20/2024) and informed consent was obtained from human subjects. Participants were recruited using postal

Fig. 1. Summary of the theoretical model to be tested in the study. * Denotes interactive effects.

invitations to a random sample of 2000 residents in the Turku study area. Residents who received the postal letter were invited to complete an online survey, which was distributed by a survey administration consultant. The survey was conducted according to the principles of informed consent and in accordance with European General Data Protection Regulation.

3.3. Survey instrument and measures

Online surveys were distributed in the local official languages—Finnish and Swedish, as well as English. Prior to survey administration, we engaged a professional translator to translate the entire survey from English to Finnish and English to Swedish to ensure appropriate alignment in wording and meaning. Since the survey was expected to elicit most responses in the local Finnish language, the Finnish translations were also evaluated by bilingual research experts in the field. We then tested the translated Finnish scale items for face validity with a sample of 10 postgraduate students and five residents from the sample area. We made minor changes to wording after the face validity test. The survey comprised of the following measures.

3.3.1. Empathy with nature

Empathy with nature was measured using a 10-item scale tested and validated by Tam et al. (2013). Principal component analysis revealed a one-factor structure. Prior to completing the scale, survey participants were asked to read the following instructions: “Nowadays, we often hear news reporting how nature is being destroyed by humans. For instance, rivers are being polluted by chemicals or toxic waste from factories, oceans being polluted by deep-water oil spill, forests being cleared and degraded into wasteland. Many animals and plants living in nature are suffering. We want to know how you think and feel when you hear this type of news according to this scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = mildly disagree, 4 = neither disagree nor agree, 5 = mildly agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree).

While empathy is not confined to negative emotions, we follow Tam et al. (2013) by focusing on how empathy is aroused by distress given that empathy is more likely to be aroused by stress than good fortune (Royzman & Kumar, 2001).

3.3.2. Cognitive and affective empathy (QCAE) with humans

We draw on the Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy (QCAE), which has been found to have high convergent and construct validity (Reniers et al., 2011). Reiners and colleagues identified five high internally valid subscales of perspective taking, online simulation, emotion contagion, proximal responsivity, and peripheral responsivity. Perspective taking and online simulation measure cognitive empathy and emotion contagion, proximal responsivity and peripheral responsivity measure affective empathy. The five-factor solution was consistent across gender. Perspective taking involves intuitively putting oneself in another person’s shoes to see things from his or her perspective. Online simulation requires imagining what that person is feeling. Emotional contagion assesses the automatic mirroring of the feelings of others. Proximal responsivity addresses the responsiveness aspect of empathic behaviour. Peripheral responsivity is like proximal responsivity, but in a detached context (*ibid*). Participants were asked to respond to each empathy item on a 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree scale.

3.3.3. Conservation behaviour

We drew on a short form 18-item conservation behaviour scale created by Barbett et al. (2020). Separate components of ‘individual’ and ‘organised’ engagement in the public/civil sphere and private garden sphere were identified, consistent with more generic conservation behaviours found by Stern (2000). Items in the organised public sphere relate to petitioning, practical volunteering within conservation and other behaviours not directly tied to green spaces. Items in the private

sphere relate to planting and maintain pollinator-friendly species (Barbett et al., 2020). Participants were asked to respond to each item on a 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree scale.

While Barbett and colleagues focused on self-reported past behaviour, we also reframed each statement into a set of behaviour intention statements, reflecting respondents’ intentions to engage in public and private gardening conservation behaviours over the coming 12 months. Previous research has found stronger associations between motivations and behavioural intentions than past behaviours (Steg & Vlek, 2009), and therefore we deemed it important to test both forms of behaviour in this study.

3.3.4. Socio-demographics

Participants were asked to self-report their age, gender, highest level of education, and monthly income level (see Table 1).

3.4. Analyses

3.4.1. Testing the internal validity of empathy and behavioural constructs

We assessed the reliability of all latent constructs using Cronbach’s alpha and conducted separate confirmatory factor analysis for the items within each construct. Factor loadings were considered significant if they exceeded 0.4 and all factors were subjected to Promax rotation and Kaiser normalization before extraction.

To determine the number of factors to retain, we relied on a combination of the Kaiser criterion (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994) and parallel analysis (Russell, 2002). The Kaiser criterion suggests that all factors with an eigenvalue, or k value, over 1 (Hair & Sarstedt, 2019, p. 20), while parallel analysis is a simulation-based approach (Russell, 2002). In our case, parallel analysis involved comparing the eigenvalues produced by conducting CFAs on our survey data with a set of eigenvalues produced by CFAs conducted on randomly generated data. In total, 100 random datasets were created per concept. A factor analysis was run on each dataset and the resulting eigenvalues were saved. The range of eigenvalues based on random data across each group of 100 runs was then compared to the eigenvalues produced from the observed data (Supporting Material 1).

3.4.2. Assessing the relationships between socio-demographics, empathy and conservation behaviour

We used linear regression to evaluate potential impacts of socio-demographics on empathy with humans, empathy with nature, and conservation behaviour before also examining the relationships between empathy with humans, empathy with nature and conservation behaviour. To gain insight into direct and indirect relationships, we employed a stepwise approach. In Block 1, we included socio-demographic variables to control for background characteristics. In Block 2 we added the

Table 1
Socio-demographics of survey respondents.

		n (%)		
		Female	Male	Total
Age	15–29 years	20 (9.8)	13 (11.1)	33 (10.2)
	30–44 years	60 (29.3)	19 (16.2)	79 (24.5)
	45–59 years	34 (16.6)	20 (17.1)	54 (16.8)
	60–74 years	59 (28.8)	43 (36.8)	101 (31.7)
	>75 years	32 (15.6)	22 (18.8)	54 (16.8)
Education	Elementary and secondary	38 (18.5)	21 (17.9)	59 (18.3)
	Professional training	32 (15.6)	20 (17.1)	52 (16.1)
	Undergraduate	71 (34.6)	41 (35.0)	112 (34.8)
	Postgraduate or higher	64 (31.2)	25 (29.9)	99 (30.7)
Income	<3000 Euros per month	125 (61.0)	63 (53.8)	188 (58.4)
	3000–5000 Euros per month	55 (26.8)	44 (37.6)	99 (30.7)
	>5000 Euros per month	25 (12.2)	19 (8.5)	35 (10.9)

base empathy measures to examine their unique contribution beyond demographics. In Block 3 we introduced the empathy related interaction among empathy with nature and cognitive and affective empathy. Finally, in Block 4 we included behavioural intention to assess its predictive value on private and public conservation behaviour. Socio-demographic variables (Age, Gender, Education, and Income) were reduced to a set of binaries. Age and Income were reduced to three binary variables each, with the middle category being used as a baseline category to avoid multicollinearity. Age was recoded into 15–29 years, 30–43 years, and >44 years, with 30–43 years being the baseline category. Undergraduate and postgraduate training was recoded into at least university level training and non-university training. Income was recoded into <3000 Euros/month, 3000–5000 Euros per month, and >5000 Euros per month, with the baseline being 3000–5000 Euros per month.

3.5. Structural equation modelling of the effects of socio-demographic factors and empathy on conservation behaviour

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to further evaluate the direct and indirect effects of empathy on socio-demographics and empathy on conservation behaviour, as this approach enables the simultaneous testing of multiple relationships within a single model. SEM's ability to model these pathways concurrently has the potential to better capture complex interplay between variables and thus provide a more comprehensive overview of the pathways linking socio-demographics (age, gender, education, income), empathy dimensions (empathy with humans, empathy with nature), and conservation behaviour. Rather than simultaneously evaluating of all latent constructs, the factors extracted in the CFA was used as a base for the SEM, a parcelling approach serving to reduce model complexity and facilitate comparison with previous regression results.

4. Results

4.1. Participant background

Out of the 2000 individuals prompted to take part in this study, a total of 329 people answered the survey, giving an overall response rate of 16.5 %. No respondents answered the Swedish language version of the survey, 12 people answered in English, and 317 people responded in Finnish. The resulting data displayed a balanced demographic composition, with similar proportions of females and males across all age, education and income groups (Table 1). A key exception was a gender imbalance in the 30–44 years age group, which contained a lower proportion of men (16.2 %) than women (29.3 %). Compared to Turku census data (Statistics Finland, 2023), 10.2 % of our respondents were in the 15–29 age group, compared to 23.2 % in the total population; our sample also included a higher proportion of respondents in the 60–74 age bracket 31.7 % versus 25.0 %. This indicates a slight skew towards older respondents, a pattern commonly observed in online survey studies (Salminen et al., 2025).

Confirmatory factor analysis revealed that scale items cohered around three components of empathy (empathy with nature, cognitive empathy with humans, affective empathy with humans) in accordance with established theory (Table 2). Empathy with nature scale items accounted for 63 % of the total variance in empathy with nature response, while cognitive empathy accounted for 33 % and affective empathy accounted for 31 % of the variance of empathy with humans. Acceptable levels of variance were also explained for the different behavioural constructs (Table 2). The factor loadings of individual items varied from 0.40 (I intend to vote for nature or wildlife conservation-friendly legislation in local or national elections) to 0.89 (I have planted pollinator-friendly plants). Using Kaiser criterion, all eigenvalues for latent constructs were >1. Parallel analysis identified the same factor solutions as the Kaiser criterion except for identifying a potential two factor solution for the affective empathy construct. However, this

Table 2

Factor loadings, variance explained and descriptives for empathy and behaviour items.

Item	Wording	Factor loading	M	SD
Empathy with nature				
	I imagine how I would feel if I were the suffering animals and plants	0.87	4.60	1.69
	I get involved with the feelings of the suffering of animals and plants	0.81	4.86	1.49
	I feel as though I were one of the suffering animals and plants	0.82	4.29	1.77
	I can very easily put myself in the place of the suffering animals and plants	0.84	4.91	1.56
	I try to understand how the suffering animals and plants feel by imagining how things look from their perspective	0.81	5.09	1.50
	I visualize in my mind clearly and vividly how the suffering animals and plants feel in their situation	0.85	4.56	1.74
	I have tender, concerned feelings for the suffering animals and plants	0.71	5.56	1.33
	I feel what the suffering animals and plants are feeling	0.80	4.34	1.77
	I feel the pain the suffering animals and plants are experiencing	0.82	4.58	1.68
	I feel sympathetic toward the suffering animals and plants	0.57	6.06	1.11
	% variance explained	63 %		
Cognitive empathy with humans				
	I can easily work out what another person might want to talk about	0.53	3.69	0.74
	I can tell if someone is masking their true emotion	0.56	3.77	0.72
	I can sense if I am intruding, even if the other person does not tell me	0.45	3.99	0.67
	I try to look at everybody's side of a disagreement before I make a decision	0.62	3.96	0.66
	Before criticizing somebody, I try to imagine how I would feel if I was in their place	0.65	3.90	0.74
	When I am upset at someone, I usually try to "put myself in their shoes"	0.59	3.53	0.81
	% variance explained	33 %		
Affective empathy with humans				
	I am happy when I am with a cheerful group and sad when the others are glum	0.50	3.77	0.82
	It worries me when others are worrying and panicky	0.56	3.25	1.03
	People I am with have a strong influence on my mood	0.55	3.67	0.87
	I usually stay emotionally detached when watching a film	0.46	2.47	0.97
	I am usually objective when I watch a film or play, and I don't often get	0.51	2.72	0.99
	I often get deeply involved with the feelings of a character in a film, play	0.64	4.41	1.00
	I often get emotionally involved with my friends' problems	0.63	3.71	0.83
	Friends talk to me about their problems as they say that I am very understanding	0.45	3.83	0.82
	It affects me very much when one of my friends seems upset	0.64	38.4	0.87
	% variance explained	31 %		
Public sphere behavioural intention				
	I intend to join local municipality meetings about nature conservation issues	0.78	2.64	1.03
	I intend to vote for nature or wildlife conservation-friendly legislation in local or national elections	0.40	4.10	0.93
	I intend to volunteer with a conservation organisation in habitat management	0.80	2.82	1.02
	% variance explained	47 %		
Private sphere behavioural intention				
	I intend to plant pollinator-friendly plants	0.81	3.70	1.18
	I intend to plant native plants	0.81	3.42	1.16

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Item	Wording	Factor loading	M	SD
	I intend to add log piles or other materials that can be used as a home/shelter	0.74	3.35	1.17
% variance explained		79 %		
Public sphere behaviour				
	I have joined local municipality meetings about nature conservation issues	0.83	2.21	1.04
	I intend to vote for nature or wildlife conservation-friendly legislation in local or national elections	0.43	3.41	1.26
	I have volunteered with a conservation organisation in habitat management	0.83	2.35	1.08
% variance explained		70 %		
Private sphere behaviour				
	I have planted pollinator-friendly plants	0.89	3.49	1.32
	I have planted native plants	0.84	3.22	1.32
	I have added log piles or other materials that can be used as a home/shelter	0.72	3.14	1.34
% variance explained		82 %		

potential second factor was oriented towards items measuring empathy towards characters in movies or plays (Supporting Material 1), leading us to base our analysis on the single factor solution suggested by the Kaiser criterion.

Correlating the factor scores reveals several noteworthy relationships (Table 3). The correlation between empathy with nature and cognitive empathy (0.37), as well as affective empathy (0.47), shows moderate associations, indicating some relatedness while still allowing these factors to capture distinct aspects of empathy. Moreover, the correlations between public conservation behavioural intention and public conservation behaviour (0.78) and private conservation behavioural intention and private conservation behaviour (0.86) are notably high, as could be expected.

4.2. Predictive effects of socio-demographics on empathy

Socio demographics explained 13–17 % of the variation in empathy among respondents. Being female had significant strong positive effects on cognitive empathy ($B = 0.83, p < 0.001$), affective empathy ($B = 0.68, p < 0.001$) and empathy with nature ($B = 1.15, p < 0.001$) (Table 4). Being female and >44 years was a significant negative predictor of empathy with nature ($B = -0.76$), while being female and <30 years had no significant effect on empathy with nature. The strong positive effect between females and empathy with nature can therefore be largely attributed to females between the ages of 30 and 44 years. Higher incomes of >5000 €/month had significant moderate positive effects on cognitive empathy ($B = 0.35$), affective empathy ($B = 0.45$) and empathy with nature ($B = 0.33$). Interestingly, a significant negative relationship was found between university level trained respondents and empathy with nature ($B = -0.29$).

Table 3

Pearson correlation matrix showing the relationships between factor scores.

	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour	Public conservation behavioural intention	Private conservation behavioural intention	Cognitive empathy	Affective empathy
Private conservation behaviour	0.40	1.00				
Public conservation behavioural intention	0.78	0.38	1.00			
Private conservation behavioural intention	0.41	0.86	0.46	1.00		
Cognitive empathy	0.28	0.24	0.32	0.39	1.00	
Affective empathy	0.26	0.07	0.34	0.15	0.47	1.00
Empathy with nature	0.50	0.26	0.56	0.36	0.37	0.47

Table 4

The predictive effects of socio-demographics on different components of empathy (unstandardised coefficients).

VARS	Cognitive empathy	Affective empathy	Empathy with nature
	<i>B</i> (<i>SE</i>)	<i>B</i> (<i>SE</i>)	<i>B</i> (<i>SE</i>)
Gender (Female)	0.83*** (0.20)	0.68*** (0.21)	1.15*** (0.24)
Education (Uni.)	0.14 (0.10)	-0.04 (0.10)	-0.29*** (0.11)
Income (<3000 €)	0.11 (0.10)	0.06 (0.11)	0.10 (0.12)
Income (>5000 €)	0.35** (0.16)	0.45*** (0.17)	0.33* (0.19)
Age (15–29 years)	0.11 (0.27)	0.17 (0.28)	0.09 (0.31)
Age (>44 years)	-0.09 (0.19)	-0.10 (0.20)	0.38* (0.22)
Gender (Female) * Age (15–29 years)	-0.20 (0.34)	0.24 (0.35)	-0.37 (0.39)
Gender (Female) * Age (>44 years)	-0.44* (0.23)	-0.40 (0.25)	-0.76*** (0.27)
Constant	-0.49** (0.20)	-0.30 (0.21)	-0.57** (0.23)
Observations	329	329	329
R2	0.19	0.18	0.15
R2 Adj.	0.17	0.16	0.13

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

4.3. Predictive effects on behaviour

The stepwise regression approach outlined here involves progressively adding different sets of variables to predict conservation behaviour (Table 5). In Block 1, socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, and income are introduced to control for background characteristics. Block 2 adds base empathy measures to assess their contribution beyond the socio-demographics. In Block 3, empathy-related interaction terms are included to examine how empathy towards other species may influence behaviour. Finally, Block 4 introduces behavioural intention to determine its predictive value on both private and public conservation actions. A multicollinearity check was run on the Block 4 model (see supporting material). The mean Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) across all variables were 1.55 and the highest individual value was 2.14 (Empathy with Nature). Thus, multicollinearity levels are unlikely to be problematic.

Socio demographics explained 12–16 % of the variation in conservation behaviour, with the model explaining public behaviour (R^2 Adj. = 0.16) slightly better than private behaviour (R^2 Adj. = 0.12). While variables measuring empathy had little impact on this range, adding empathy with nature resulted in a marked improvement in the variance explained with the adjusted R-square increasing to 0.35. The explanatory power of the model was further increased with the introduction of the behavioural intention measurements, which increased the adjusted R-squares of the public and private behaviour to 0.63 and 0.76

Table 5

Stepwise regression showing the predictive effects of socio-demographics and empathy on different components of public and private sphere conservation behaviour.

	Block 1: Socio-demographics		Block 2: Empathy		Block 3: Interaction effects		Block 4: Behavioural intention	
	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour
Gender (Female)	0.38*** (0.09)	0.38*** (0.10)	0.13 (0.09)	0.20* (0.10)	0.15* (0.09)	0.21** (0.10)	-0.01 (0.07)	0.07 (0.06)
Education (Univ.)	-0.14 (0.10)	-0.06 (0.11)	-0.04 (0.09)	-0.05 (0.10)	-0.01 (0.09)	-0.04 (0.10)	-0.01 (0.07)	-0.02 (0.06)
Income (<3000€)	-0.20* (0.11)	-0.26** (0.11)	-0.22** (0.09)	-0.29*** (0.11)	-0.22** (0.09)	-0.29*** (0.11)	-0.19*** (0.07)	-0.13** (0.06)
Income (≥5000€)	0.52*** (0.16)	0.35** (0.17)	0.36** (0.15)	0.24 (0.17)	0.32** (0.15)	0.26 (0.17)	0.14 (0.11)	-0.00 (0.10)
Age (15–29 years)	-0.48*** (0.17)	-0.42** (0.18)	-0.39** (0.16)	-0.34* (0.18)	-0.40** (0.15)	-0.34* (0.18)	-0.14 (0.12)	-0.19* (0.10)
Age (>44)	-0.41*** (0.11)	0.20* (0.12)	-0.35*** (0.10)	0.27** (0.12)	-0.32*** (0.10)	0.27** (0.12)	-0.19** (0.08)	0.11* (0.06)
Cognitive empathy			0.06 (0.06)	0.24*** (0.06)	0.06 (0.06)	0.23*** (0.07)	0.01 (0.04)	0.03 (0.04)
Affective empathy			-0.05 (0.06)	-0.10 (0.06)	-0.08 (0.06)	-0.12* (0.07)	-0.07* (0.04)	-0.04 (0.04)
Empathy with nature			0.40*** (0.05)	0.17*** (0.06)	0.45*** (0.05)	0.20*** (0.06)	0.12*** (0.04)	-0.03 (0.04)
Cognitive * Affective					-0.10* (0.06)	-0.14* (0.07)	-0.03 (0.05)	-0.09** (0.04)
Cognitive * Nature					0.19*** (0.05)	0.10 (0.06)	0.02 (0.04)	0.05 (0.04)
Nature * Affective					0.03 (0.05)	-0.00 (0.05)	0.00 (0.04)	0.01 (0.03)
Public conservation behavioural intention							0.69*** (0.05)	0.01 (0.04)
Private conservation behavioural intention							0.04 (0.04)	0.86*** (0.03)
Constant	0.23 (0.15)	-0.17 (0.16)	0.30** (0.14)	-0.09 (0.16)	0.23 (0.14)	-0.08 (0.16)	0.26** (0.11)	0.00 (0.09)
Obs.	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329
F	11.71***	8.48***	18.88***	9.28***	15.87***	7.37***	40.54***	73.96***
R2	0.18	0.14	0.35	0.21	0.38	0.22	0.64	0.77
Adjusted R2	0.164	0.120	0.329	0.185	0.352	0.189	0.628	

***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

respectively.

In terms of variable effects, being female and having a high income of >5000 Euros is a significant predictor of both public and private sphere conservation behaviour ($B > 0.35$, $p < 0.05$, Table 5). Young (15–29 years) respondents have significantly weaker public and private conservation behaviours $B > -0.42$, $p < 0.05$ compared to middle-aged respondents (30–44 years). Cognitive empathy retains a positive effect on private conservation behaviour ($B = 0.24$) even when including empathy with nature ($B = 0.23$), however, no significant interactive effects exist between empathy with nature, affective empathy and conservation behaviour in the private sphere.

A structural equation model including behavioural intention, empathy and socio-demographics explains 65 % of public sphere conservation behaviour and 77 % of private sphere conservation behaviour (Table 6, Fig. 2). The same model explains 45 % of the variance in public sphere conservation intention and 23 % of private sphere conservation intention, while sociodemographic variables explain between 13 and 19 % of the variance in empathy (either affective, cognitive or empathy with nature). Age (>44 years) had a significant negative effect on cognitive empathy ($B = -0.38$), while the interactive effect of cognitive empathy and empathy with nature had a positive effect ($B = 0.24$) on public sphere conservation behavioural intentions. The strength of the indirect effect between age and cognitive empathy is -0.09 highlighting that cognitive empathy mediates the indirect effect of Age (>44 years)

on behaviour. Age also has a significant negative direct effect on conservation behaviour in the public sphere ($B = -0.19$), giving age a total effect of $B = -0.28$ when controlling for cognitive empathy.

While the model fit statistics are not ideal (Table 7), adding covariances between behavioural intention and behavioural measurements resulted in acceptable model fit. These covariances were not assumed in the interest of transparency.

5. Discussion

The aim of this paper was to examine the direct and indirect effects of empathy with nature, as well as cognitive and affective empathy with humans on conservation behaviour in the private and public spheres. Empathy with nature consistently predicted conservation behaviour in the public and private spheres. However, we find that two complementary systems of cognitive empathy with humans (mental perspective taking) and affective empathy with humans (sharing of emotions) have differing effects on conservation actions - cognitive empathy supported conservation action while affective empathy impeded it. In the discussion that follows, we offer a more nuanced understanding of inclusion of self in nature (Schultz, 2000) and empathy-sustainability dynamics (Brown et al., 2019) in the light of our findings and four hypotheses.

We found support for cognitive and affective empathy as being two distinctly separate capacities (Reniers et al., 2011; Shamay-Tsoory et al.,

Table 6
Structural equation model showing the direct and interactive effects of socio-demographics and empathy on behaviour.

	Effect on:						
	Cognitive empathy	Affective empathy	Empathy with nature	Public conservation behavioural intention	Private conservation behavioural intention	Public conservation behaviour	Private conservation behaviour
	B(SE)	B(SE)	B(SE)	B(SE)	B(SE)	B(SE)	B(SE)
Public conservation behavioural intention						0.69*** (-0.05)	0.01 (-0.04)
Private conservation behavioural intention						0.04 (-0.04)	0.86*** (-0.03)
Cognitive empathy				0.05 (-0.05)	0.23*** (-0.06)	0.01 (-0.04)	0.03 (-0.04)
Affective empathy				-0.01 (-0.05)	-0.10 (-0.06)	-0.07* (-0.04)	-0.04 (-0.04)
Empathy with nature				0.46*** (-0.05)	0.27*** (-0.06)	0.12** (-0.04)	-0.03 (-0.04)
Gender (Female)	0.51*** (-0.09)	0.44*** (-0.09)	0.59*** (-0.1)	0.22** (-0.08)	0.15 (-0.10)	-0.01 (-0.07)	0.07 (-0.06)
Education (Univ.)	0.14 (-0.09)	-0.04 (-0.10)	-0.28** (-0.11)	0.01 (-0.08)	-0.01 (-0.10)	-0.01 (-0.07)	-0.02 (-0.06)
Income (<3000€)	0.08 (-0.1)	0.02 (-0.11)	0.05 (-0.12)	-0.03 (-0.08)	-0.19* (-0.10)	-0.19** (-0.07)	-0.13** (-0.06)
Income (≥5000€)	0.38** (-0.16)	0.48*** (-0.17)	0.40** (-0.18)	0.24* (-0.14)	0.31 (-0.16)	0.14 (-0.11)	0.00 (-0.09)
Age (>30)	-0.04 (-0.17)	0.30* (-0.17)	-0.18 (-0.19)	-0.36** (-0.14)	-0.17 (-0.17)	-0.14 (-0.12)	-0.19* (-0.1)
Age (>44)	-0.38*** (-0.11)	-0.36*** (-0.11)	-0.14 (-0.12)	-0.20** (-0.09)	0.19* (-0.11)	-0.19** (-0.08)	0.11* (-0.06)
Cognitive * Affective				-0.10* (-0.05)	-0.05 (-0.07)	-0.03 (-0.05)	-0.09** (-0.04)
Cognitive * Nature				0.24*** (-0.05)	0.05 (-0.06)	0.02 (-0.04)	0.05 (-0.03)
Affective* Nature				0.03 (-0.04)	-0.01 (-0.05)	0.00 (-0.03)	0.01 (-0.03)
Constant	-0.25 (-0.15)	-0.11 (-0.15)	-0.15 (-0.17)	-0.04 (-0.13)	-0.1 (-0.15)	0.26** (-0.1)	0.00 (-0.09)
R2	0.19	0.17	0.13	0.45	0.23	0.66	0.77
Observations	329	329	329	329	329	329	329

Fig. 2. Adapted model showing significant relationships between empathy and conservation behavioural intention and past behaviour (behaviour).

2009), and cognitive and affective empathy being conceptually and empirically distinct to empathy with nature (supporting H1). The consistently weak to moderate positive associations between cognitive empathy and empathy with nature, and affective empathy and empathy with nature is to be expected given that we did not force subjects to pit empathy with nature against empathy with humans (Cameron et al.,

2019, 2022).

In accordance with H2 and previous studies (Tam, 2013; Wang et al., 2023), empathy with nature was a moderate to strong predictor of conservation behaviour intention (Table 6). This finding generally supports inclusion of self in nature, empathy-altruism and empathy-sustainability hypotheses that people with stronger nature

Table 7

Goodness of fit statistics for the structural equation model.

Measurement	Full model	Excluding Demographics
Root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.22	0.27
Comparative fit index (CFI)	0.85	0.95
Tucker–Lewis index (TLI)	0.08	0.31
Standardized root mean squared residual	0.07	0.06
Coefficient of determination (CD)	0.58	0.49

relatedness and emotional connection to the natural world exhibit stronger willingness to engage in conservation actions (Tam, 2013; Brown et al., 2019; Schultz, 2000; Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, cognitive empathy was a moderate, positive predictor of conservation behaviour intention in the private sphere, suggesting that the ability to understand other human's emotions is an important way to process behaviour linked to specific conservation actions around the home, such as the planting of native vegetation. Research on pro-social behaviour provides supporting evidence for the direct effects between cognitive empathy and behaviour (Unger & Thumulari, 1997; Van Lissa et al., 2017).

The positive interactive effects between empathy with nature and cognitive empathy and behaviour also offers preliminary support for consideration of 'multispecies empathy' in behaviour assessments. By multispecies empathy, we draw attention to the interconnections between empathy for humans and other species, drawing on Edith Stein's model that empathy leads to intersubjectivity and a shared construction of the world (see Schütz, 1932). More recent multispecies justice scholarship refers to the concept of 'entangled empathy' (Gruen, 2015), requiring responsibilities towards 'others' with whom we are bound together, including minorities and threatened animals and plants in cities (Celermajer et al., 2021). It also requires integrating the perspectives of other species into ecosystem management (Schnegg & Breyer, 2024; Raymond et al., 2025).

While people can rationalise the biodiversity crisis and can act based on their cognitive awareness of the needs of humans and other species, we found that affective empathy can impede conservation actions and can negatively mediate the relationship between cognitive empathy and behaviour (Fig. 2). Affective empathy had a negative effect on public sphere conservation behaviour although showing weak relationships (H2). This might mean that participants having high affective empathy towards humans may not necessarily transpose it to others species. It may be also possible that the propensity to have strong negative emotions like fear and distress with respect to other humans (e.g., misfortune of many individuals) could serve as a barrier to conservation action. In social psychology, components of affective empathy like personal distress have been found to have no or contrary effects on pro-social behaviour (Carrera et al., 2013; Schroeder et al., 1988). Hence, we argue for a multi-level understanding of the empathy-sustainability hypothesis emphasising the extent to which individuals view themselves to be (cognitively and affectively) engaged in both nature and the lives of other humans. Conservation actions will not only depend upon to which extent individuals hold biospheric or altruistic concerns, but the cognitive and affective processes through which they direct empathy towards humans and other species. Further supporting evidence comes from place attachment scholarship, which has found that the nature and strength of our relationships to the personal, natural and social contexts of place differentially affect conservation actions (building on Raymond et al., 2010; 2011).

Consistent with H3, females generally self-reported stronger empathy with nature and empathy with humans than males (consistent with Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004; Jolliffe & Farrington, 2004; Silke et al., 2018), and were more likely to intend to engage in conservation behaviours in the public sphere. These effects were most salient for females between the ages of 30 and 44 years. The identified negative

relationship between education level and behaviour is supported by Ratinen and Linnanen (2022) who found that education does not have significant effects on Finns' environmental awareness. Similarly, the finding that youth tend to have more negative environmental attitudes is supported by Hyry (2017).

We found partial support that socio-demographics confound the relationships between empathy and conservation behaviour (H4). A model including empathy with nature and the interactive effects between empathy with nature and cognitive empathy explains more than double the amount of variance in conservation behaviour intention in the public sphere (R-squared Adj. = 0.41) than a model with only socio-demographic factors and cognitive empathy (R-squared Adj. = 0.19) and affective empathy (R-squared Adj. = 0.21).

5.1. Limitations and future directions

This study relied on the recruitment of subjects via a push-to-web survey complemented by panel members. The response rate of 16.5 % is relatively low, which is a commonly reported limitation in online participatory studies (Salminen et al., 2025). Due to the small sample size, it is important to acknowledge that the results cannot be generalized to the population level or different social groups. For example, our socio-demographic sample was relatively representative of the Finnish population above 15 years of age, but vulnerable groups such as new migrants remained under-represented. Future research should aim for larger and more balanced samples to examine whether the empathy-behaviour relationships found here are reliable among various socio-cultural groups.

In addition, Finnish translation of the semantic scales used in the survey was not systematically validated, which may lead to challenges with equivalence, validity and capturing cultural differences. Although in this study we used a local-language test group to evaluate the usability and face-validity of the questions, future research can employ simple back-translation approaches (Brislin, 1970) or more rigorous validation protocols (Aletta et al., 2024) to achieve confirmation of results through triangulation processes.

Given the large number of variables considered in this study, it was not possible to test all confounding and bidirectional relationships in our empathy-behaviour model. Like in many conservation behaviour studies, we tested the empathy-behaviour intention-behaviour pathway. It is possible that alternative pathways exist; for example, engaging in conservation behaviour over the long term could promote empathy with nature and humans. Such mediation models could be tested in future research. In addition, choice contexts and measures of positive and negative affective empathy could be also integrated to better understand the multi-level relationships between empathy and conservation behaviour.

While we assessed both empathy with nature and empathy with humans, it was challenging to fully understand 'multispecies empathy' based on the survey techniques employed. Future research could experiment with eco-acoustics as a pathway for improving the quality of nature-based experiences for humans, and thus fostering new ways to 'listen in' to other species (Eldridge et al., 2020; Francis et al., 2017). For example, hearing the 'cry of the wild' is now considered a key first step on our path to attending to the lived experience of animals and the non-human side of human-animal relations (Carruthers-Jones et al., 2019; Gibbs, 2020). Soundwalks which take us on a listening journey into this soundscape, create an experience with nature, a multispecies extension of the idea that "walking with others – sharing their step, style and rhythm – creates an affinity, empathy or sense of belonging with them" (Pink et al., 2017, p. 111). Virtual reality (VR) also provides novel opportunities given its ability to induce emotional response and promote nature connectedness (Brambilla et al., 2024; Diniz Bernardo et al., 2021). In the near future, VR technology may transform emotion elicitation methods by enhancing "perspective taking" to generate cognitive empathy (van Loon et al., 2018) and produce affective representations of

reality through three active dimensions – immersion, presence, and embodiment (Barbot & Kaufman, 2020).

6. Conclusion

This paper demonstrated the importance of both empathy with nature and empathy with humans (particularly cognitive empathy) on conservation behaviour. We build on previous research by highlighting the importance of moving beyond general measures of empathy with humans to models that consider the direct, indirect and interactive effects among empathy with nature, cognitive empathy with humans, affective empathy with humans and behaviour. Facilitating cognitive awareness of fellow human needs and the needs of other species is critical for driving conservation actions, highlighting the crucial importance of educational programs in facilitating awareness about the importance of biodiversity conservation, and possibilities for conserving it in both public and private spheres.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christopher M. Raymond: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Max Eriksson:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Silviya Korpilo:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jonathan Carruthers-Jones:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2025.102710>.

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